

The role of Libraries as per New Education Policy:

Dr. Jyoti Magar*

Ramiladevi Patil Art's and Science College Neknour Dist. Beed (431125)

ABSTRACT

This paper reviews the revisions included in NEP 2020 in general and investigates its impact on LIS education in particular. This paper reviews present LIS education at UG and PG levels and proposes changes in its framework in line with its preparedness for NEP 2020. The paper discusses the history of LIS education and illustrates the International LIS training. The adoption of NEP 2020 and its impact on LIS education is illustrated. This paper draws a framework on design of LIS education. This article discusses the importance of Libraries in teaching and learning and highlights the role of libraries for all levels of education. Now a day the Libraries support 24x7 hours access to its resources for the growth of knowledge and skills of the users. The Library resources are for use by the readers and hence are as important as food for human life. In rapidly transforming our education system, the library resources and users have undergone drastic changes. Today's Libraries store knowledge and information in digital form for all age group people like the students, teacher, scientist, politician and general public of transforming society throughout the world. The role of Libraries as per New Education Policy of India will increase many folds.

Keywords: role of Libraries, Education Policy

INTRODUCTION

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are as follows:

1. To increase awareness about the New Education Policy 2020;
2. To highlight the role of library in education system;
3. To discuss changing landscape of learning and education;
4. To develop adequate Library resources.

Research Methodology

This article has been brought out on the basis of evaluation of recent literature published on the internet and **other** relevant sources and is kind of descriptive study. It is an attempt being made to understand and evaluate the use of Libraries as an integral part of our education system.

Point of Views from Library Professional;

The NEP emphasizes the teachers and faculty, including the library professionals, to have a positive attitude of service. Keeping that in mind, the library becomes the educational service center of limitless resources in print, digital, and personnel.

For effectively laid down the principles of NEP, the collaboration of library professionals with teachers is

the best practices for better outcome of education. Thus, this can be done by pursuing Curiosity & Passion Projects through cluster groups.

Revamp the Collection of Library

- Knowledge of India: ancient and modern
- Environmental awareness including water and resource conservation, sanitation and hygiene
- Current affairs and understanding of critical issues facing local communities
- The specialties of each state, countries and the world around
- Tribal and indigenous knowledge
- All forms of literature in national and International level
- A multi-disciplinary approach to all subjects**

Colleges and universities library role:

Following are the some important role of college and universities libraries for the promotion and progress in knowledge.

1. Facilitate the development and execution of educational programmed that equip students with the abilities to thrive or adapt in a social and economic context that is always changing.

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2. It offers and promotes student efficiency and enhances the academic, aesthetic, societal and emotional development of students.
3. It allows the person to achieve spiritual, inspiring and recreational activities via reading. Besides this, a library also plays an important role in education including: [28]
4. Helping literacy to become permanent.
5. Enables the individual to develop their full potential and to expand their perspective, involvement and abilities,
6. It improves literacy and reading habits among children and Young adults.
7. It also promotes readings amongst the local communities.
8. It prepares the person to prepare for future including job search and other works. [26]

Highlights Of NEP 2020 For Higher Education

- Internationalisation
- Enhance GER To 50% By The Year 2035
- Holistic & Multidisciplinary Education
- Autonomy and Accountability
- Inclusivity and Equity
- Research and Innovation
- Curriculum Flexibility and Credit Transfer

- Digitalization Of Teaching-Learning Process
- Dismantling of the 'UGC' And 'AICTE'
- Skill Development and Vocational Education
- Financial Support to Assist Students
- Encouragement to Use Indian Languages
- Technology in Education
- Rationalized Education Architecture
- Distance Learning/Open Learning
- Imparting Professional Education

Holistic & Multidisciplinary Education!

Research and Innovation!

Enhance GER TO 50% By the Year 2035!

Internationalisation!

Digitalization of Teaching-Learning Process!

Distance Learning/ Open Learning!

Curriculum Flexibility and Credit Transfer!

Dismantling of the 'UGC' And 'AICTE'20!

Skill Development and Vocational Education!

Financial Support to Assist Students.!

Technology in Education!

Encouragement to Use Indian Languages

An introduction to Academic College Libraries

and

new

Education Policy in Parbhani District :

Sr.No	College Name	College Code	Website	Purchase of Books as per NEP
1	Shri Shivaji College, Vasmat Road, Parbhani	201	www.Kkmcollege.org	Yes
2	D. S. M.'s Arts Commerce & Science College, Jintur Road, Parbhani	202	www.dnyanopasak.org.in	Yes
3	Late Sow. Kamlatai Jamkar Mahila Mahavidalaya, Jintur Road Parbhani	203	www.lskjmm.org	Yes
4	Nutan Mahavidyalaya, Selu Dist.Parbhani	204	www.nutansansthasylu.org	Yes
5	D.S.M.'s Arts Commerce & Science College, Jintur Dist.Parbhani	205	www.justdial.com	Yes
6	K. K. M. Arts Commerce & Science College, Manwat Dist. Parbhan	206	www.kkmcollege.org	Yes
7	Shri Sant Janabai Arts Commerce Science College, Gangakhed Dist. Parbhani	207	www.justdial.com	Yes
8	Shri Gurubudhi Swami Mahavidyalaya, Purna	211	www.sgbmpurna.in	Yes

REFERENCE

1. Asif, M., & Singh, K. K. (2022). Libraries @ national education policy (NEP 2020) in India.

- Indian Journal of Library Science and Information Technology, 7(1), 18-21. <https://doi.org/10.18231/j.ijlsit.2022.004>.
2. Azim, M. A., & Ajahar, S. (2022). Higher Education in India and Japan: A Comparative Study. *IJFMR*, 4(6). <https://doi.org/10.36948/ijfmr.2022.v04i06.948>
 3. Development, Resource. (2020). National Education Policy 2020. *Economic Political Weekly*, 55(31), 4L. Retrieved from https://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/NEP_Final_English_0.pdf.
 4. Ibrahim, S. M. A. S., & Pa'anga, H. S. (2022). An Overview of New Education Policy 2020. *SUMEDHA Journal of Management*, 11(2), 74-80. <https://doi.org/10.46454/sumedha/11.2.2022.429>.
 5. K. C., T. (2022). Impact of National Education Policy 2020 on Higher Education. *SUMEDHA Journal of Management*, 11(2), 27-35. DOI <https://doi.org/10.46454/sumedha/11.2.2022.422>
 6. Lamani, M. (2021). New Education Policy-2020: Role of Libraries. *International Journal of Research in Library Science*, 7(3), 166-171. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.26761/ijrls.7.3.2021.1436>
 7. Ministry of Education. (2022). Salient Features of NEP-2020. Retrieved from <https://pib.gov.in/PressReleaseIframePage.aspx?PRID=1847066>.
 8. <http://www.kkmcollege.org/>
 9. <http://www.dnyanopasak.org.in/>
 10. <http://www.lskjmm.org/>
 11. <http://www.nutansansthasylu.org/>
 12. <http://www.justdial.com/>
 13. <http://www.kkmcollege.org/>
 14. <http://www.justdial.com/>
 15. <http://www.sgbmpurna.in/>

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